

Wide-angle and simultaneously wideband blazing (deflection) enabling multifunctionality in metagratings comprising epsilon-near-zero materials

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This paper investigates diffractions by gratings made of a dispersive material in an epsilon-near-zero (ENZ) regime and having one-side corrugations, and those made by two-component dielectric-ENZ gratings with the inner corrugations and flat outer interfaces. The goal is to achieve wideband and simultaneously wide-angle – 1st order blazing (deflection) that may enable wideband spatial filtering and demultiplexing in reflection mode. Several typical scenarios are discussed, which differ in the maximum magnitude of the blazed wave and size of the blazing area observed on the frequency-incidence angle plane, as well as the contribution of the ranges of positive and negative permittivity in the vicinity of zero. The high capability of ENZ and dielectric-ENZ gratings in asymmetric reflection is demonstrated for three different levels of losses for the dispersive material.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Gratings made of dispersive materials play an important role in modern optical and terahertz technology. First of all, subwavelength plasmonic gratings that comprise metals below plasma frequency are well known [1–4]. Diffraction gratings made of various plasmonic materials may offer a myriad of functionalities, which depend on the choice of material, geometry, and operating frequency. Natural materials and artificial plasmonic (meta-)materials with Drude and Drude–Lorentz or similar dispersion also show a near-zero-index/epsilon-near-zero (ENZ) region. This region may yield a variety of fascinating effects like near-zero phase advancement, separation of space and time variables, supercoupling, size and shape independent resonators, and others [5–11]. The potential of most of them in diverse transmission, radiation, and propagation regimes is well studied, but not yet fully exploited in diffraction gratings. The ENZ regime can be achieved, for instance, by using transparent conductive oxides, like ITO [12–14], or polar dielectrics [15–20]. Other materials such as phase-charge materials, which

have earlier been used in reconfigurable metasurfaces [21,22], may have high potential as ENZ materials [23] and this use has not yet been properly exploited. For these materials, the real part of the permittivity typically passes through zero while gradually varying the biasing parameter at frequencies that are much lower than for metals. In addition, wire media [24,25], various metallo-dielectric composites including multilayers [26,27], and Dirac cone effects [26] are worth mentioning. Diffraction gratings based on ENZ materials may enable, among others, asymmetric location of the frequency-domain thresholds for nonzero diffraction orders and one of the approaches to asymmetric transmission (AT) [17,28–32].

Various types of blazed diffraction (meta-)gratings were suggested, which may enable nearly perfect transfer of the incident-wave energy to one of higher diffraction orders. They include diffraction gratings with a special/complex structure of the period and photonic-crystal gratings [28,33–41]. Recently, meta-gratings and meta-arrays with similar functionality have been suggested [42–51]. The terms anomalous reflection and anomalous refraction have often been used in recent studies

[47,49], in spite of the fact that the wave processes fully agree with the fundamentals of the diffraction gratings theory [52]. In particular, attention has been paid to wideband and simultaneously wide-angle blazing [33,43,45,53,54]. The gratings showing this blazing regime may be particularly suitable for spatial filtering (SF) and demultiplexing. The capability of ENZ materials for SF and demultiplexing has not yet been fully explored; however, near-zero phase advancement and spectral extension of reflection and transmission features in the case of ENZ materials are expected to enable wideband and wide-angle operation. Different approaches to SF [33,55–63] and demultiplexing [64–68] were suggested, but only a part of them is connected with wideband and simultaneously wide-angle blazing. At the same time, diverse scenarios of multifunctional operation attracted a lot of attention [69–71]; among them, the ones enabled by wideband/wide-angle blazing [40,45].

In this paper, we numerically studied diffraction metagratings of two types: (i) ENZ gratings with one-side corrugations and (ii) two-component dielectric-ENZ gratings with a corrugated inner interface, while the outer interfaces are kept flat. The main goal of this study is to demonstrate the capability of diffraction metagratings based on dispersive ENZ materials in wideband and simultaneously wide-angle blazing. Here, we refer to a dispersive material as ENZ material when the real part of the relative permittivity is either positive or negative and its absolute value is less than 0.4. In fact, the studied structures do not need surface plasmons (in contrast to [53]) or guided-mode effects (in contrast to [46]).

Regarding possible applications, the emphasis will be put on the elementary functionalities, which include SF, demultiplexing, and retroreflection. It is assumed that by using the elementary functionalities various multifunctional scenarios can be designed. The role of the ranges of positive and negative ENZ permittivity will be discussed, as well as the role of the losses in the ENZ material. Similar to the earlier work [72], the grating designs will be studied, which have only one corrugated interface that is either an air-ENZ or a dielectric-ENZ interface. However, in contrast to it, we performed three tasks: (i) We studied dispersive ENZ materials; (ii) We considered transmission and reflection within wide ranges in the frequency-incidence angle plane; and (iii) We analyzed application of the studied blazing regime to the functionalities mentioned above. Moreover, for the metagratings of the both types, forward-to-backward asymmetry in reflection was investigated. Simulations were performed by using the coupled integral equations technique [73]. The main attention was paid to the case when only one nonzero diffraction order ($m \neq 0$) might propagate. The results will also be presented for the case when two or more diffraction orders propagated. The purpose is to retrieve the main functionality-enabling diffraction features in the purely ENZ and two-phase; i.e., dielectric-ENZ gratings as a step toward practical realization. Particular designs, however, are beyond the scope of this paper.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Geometry and Method

The general geometry of the two proposed gratings is shown in Fig. 1(a). The first of them represents a finite-thickness grating

Fig. 1. (a) General geometry and permittivity of the studied diffraction gratings (two periods are shown) along with schematic showing incident and outgoing waves, used coordinate system, wavevector \mathbf{k} , electric-field vector \mathbf{E} , and magnetic-field vector \mathbf{H} . (b) $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ (solid lines) and $\text{Im } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ (dashed lines) at $\omega_p L/c = 3.8, 6.28,$ and 7.8 . The corresponding values are shown near the lines, for $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$. (c) Same as (b) but for $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.05$.

with one-side corrugations, which is made of an ENZ material. In this case, the upper component (shown in gray) is assumed to be air, whereas the lower one is the ENZ component. The second one represents a stack of two gratings, one of which is made of an ENZ material and the other is made from a conventional dielectric. In this case, the upper grating (shown in gray) is assumed to be dielectric. Throughout the paper, D is the structure thickness, b is the mid-height of the corrugated part of the structure, and $2h$ means the corrugation depth, so that $b + h \leq D$. The studied structures are assumed to be periodic with period L and infinitely long in the x direction and are illuminated by a linearly polarized plane wave that is obliquely incident at angle θ . The boundary between the upper and the lower parts of the grating is given by

$$y(x) = b + h \cos(2\pi x/L). \quad (1)$$

For the sake of definiteness, permittivity of the ENZ material is given, according to the Drude model, as

$$\epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} = 1 - \omega_p/[\omega(\omega + i\gamma)], \quad (2)$$

where ω_p is the angular plasma frequency, γ is the angular collision frequency, $\omega = 2\pi f$ is angular frequency, f is frequency, and c is the speed of light. Examples of dependences of $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ and $\text{Im } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ are presented in Figs. 1(b) and 1(c) in the vicinity of $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} = 0$. For the dielectric part of the grating of the first and second types, we took $\epsilon_d = 1$ and $\epsilon_d = 2.1$, respectively. The study was performed for the case in which the electric field vector was parallel to the z axis (TE polarization).

The wave incident at arbitrary angle θ is given by

$$E^i(x, y) = E_0 \exp(i\alpha_0 x - i\beta_0 y), \quad (3)$$

where E_0 is the electric-field amplitude, $\alpha_0 = k \sin \theta$, and $\beta_0 = k \cos \theta$; $k = \omega/c$ is the free-space wavenumber. The electric field

151 above and below the grating is expressed, respectively, by

$$E^+(x, y) = E^i(x, y) + \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_m \exp(i\alpha_m x + i\beta_m y), \quad (4)$$

152 where $\beta_m = \sqrt{k^2 - \alpha_m^2}$, $\text{Im } \beta_m \geq 0$, $\alpha_m = \alpha_0 + 2\pi m/L$, ρ_m is
153 the amplitude of m th-order reflected wave, and

$$E^-(x, y) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \tau_m \exp(i\alpha_m x - i\beta_m y), \quad (5)$$

154 where τ_m is the amplitude of the m th-order transmitted wave.

155 The coupled integral equation technique is used for the
156 purposes of numerical study. The equations are solved with
157 controllable convergence and accuracy by using the fast iterative
158 algorithm; details can be found in [73]. The calculation
159 region (i.e., one structural period) is shown in Fig. 1(a) by dotted
160 green lines.

161 Once the amplitudes at the upper and lower boundaries
162 of the calculation region were found, the values of ρ_m and
163 τ_m were directly calculated. We used m th-order reflectances
164 $r_m = \rho_m \rho_m^* \text{Re } \beta_m / W$ and m th-order transmittances $t_m =$
165 $\tau_m \tau_m^* \text{Re } \beta_m / W$ to calculate fields in the far zone. Here, W
166 means the energy of the incident wave and an asterisk means
167 a complex conjugate. Note that $R + T + A = 1$, where
168 $R = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} r_m$ is the overall reflectance, $T = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} t_m$
169 is the overall transmittance, and A is the absorptance.

170 The angle of the m th-order outgoing wave can be found from
171 the grating equation [52]

$$\sin \phi_m = \sin \theta + 2\pi m/kL, \quad (6)$$

172 where $m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$. The angles ϕ_m and θ are mea-
173 sured, respectively, in the clockwise and the counter-clockwise
174 direction from the axis y ; kL represents, in fact, the normal-
175 ized frequency. If formally $|\sin \phi_m| > 1$, then the m th order
176 is evanescent; in other words, $|\sin \theta + 2\pi m/kL| = 1$ is the
177 frequency-domain threshold condition for the order m .

178 The lines of equal ϕ_{-1} as a function of kL and θ are shown in
179 Fig. 2 along with the angle and frequency dependent thresholds
180 for the orders $m = -1, +1$, and -2 . These thresholds delimit
181 the region where $m = -1$ is the only higher order that is allowed
182 to propagate. This region is of particular importance since
183 single-beam blazing is possible there due to the order $m = -1$.
184 However, it may happen that most of the incident-wave energy
185 is taken by the order $m = 0$; i.e., the blazing would not be the
186 dominant wave process. Notably, at least two higher diffraction
187 orders must be propagating to obtain $\phi_{-1} > 0$, so the maximal
188 transfer of energy to the order $m = -1$ is even more challenging
189 in this case. Besides, the retroreflection regime (i.e., $\phi_{-1} = -\theta$)
190 may appear in the region mentioned above so that the ϕ_{-1}
191 variable from -90° to nearly -20° is obtainable.

192 B. Case of One Propagating Higher Order

193 Now, let us discuss the transmission and reflection results
194 obtained in the case for which only one of the higher propagat-
195 ing orders may propagate. Figure 3 shows t_{-1} and r_{-1} in the
196 (kL, θ) -plane for $\omega_p L/c = 3.8$, so $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} = 0$ is achieved at
197 $kL = 3.8$. For the ENZ grating, called EG1, it is observed in

Fig. 2. Lines of the equal angle of the -1 st order outgoing wave ϕ_{-1} (denoted by its value; i.e., from -75° to $+5^\circ$ - dotted lines). Thresholds of the orders $m = -1$, $m = +1$, and $m = -2$ are shown by the solid lines; and retroreflection regime, $\phi_{-1} = -\theta$ is shown by the dashed black line.

Fig. 3. (a), (c), and (e) Transmittance t_{-1} and (b), (d), and (f) reflectance r_{-1} shown on (kL, θ) -plane at $D/L = 1.5$, $b/D = 0.50$, $h/D = 0.40$, $\omega_p L/c = 3.8$, and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$ for: (a) and (b) ENZ grating (EG1), (c) and (d) hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating (DEG1), and (e) and (f) dielectric grating (DG1). Insets show one structure's period: ENZ (black), dielectric (gray), and air (white).

198 Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) that two large areas exist for $m = -1$ in the
199 (kL, θ) -plane, within which t_{-1} and r_{-1} achieve the values up to
200 0.3 and 0.7, respectively. Both ranges of $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} < 0$ and
201 $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$ contribute to the area of large r_{-1} in Fig. 3(b);
202 i.e., the changing sign of $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ does not yield new features in
203 the behavior of r_{-1} .

204 This area enables high capability of the studied grating in
205 such applications reflection-mode spatial filtering (SF) and
206 demultiplexing. Indeed, taking a kL value from the considered

range, for instance, $kL = 3.9$, we can see that bandpass SF that extends nearly from 48° to 57° can be obtained. At $\theta = 48^\circ$ and 57° , $\phi_{-1} \approx -60^\circ$ and -51° , respectively; compare to Fig. 2. Similarly, bandpass but rather low-efficiency SF is achieved for $m = -1$ in the transmission mode, when $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} > 0$.

For spatial demultiplexing, it is crucial to have high and nearly the same diffraction efficiency within a wide kL range while θ is fixed. In this case, different spectral components of the incident polychromatic wave will create the outgoing waves with different values of ϕ_{-1} . Similarly, monochromatic waves incident at the given angle θ will go out at different ϕ_{-1} . For example, it may occur at $\theta = 54^\circ$, at which r_{-1} is high at least at $3.7 < kL < 4.1$, where both regimes of $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} < 0$ and $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$ are involved. In this case, ϕ_{-1} is varied nearly from -63° to -46° . Note that the areas of maximal r_{-1} and t_{-1} in the (kL, θ) -plane do not coincide, so transmission mode and reflection mode deflection processes are separated; i.e., they occupy different regions of the (kL, θ) -plane.

Stacking the EG1 grating with the complementary grating made of a low- ε dielectric material $\varepsilon_d = 2.1$ yields a hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating called DEG1, as shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d). Dramatic changes in the behavior of r_{-1} and t_{-1} are observed, as compared to EG1 grating. First, t_{-1} now becomes stronger, even though the outer corrugations are absent [74]. Second, the area of large r_{-1} is localized in the (kL, θ) -plane at a rather large θ and extends up to the grazing incidence angles. Here, it corresponds to $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} < 0$. The observed features make possible bandpass SF in transmission mode [say, at $kL = 4.65$ ($\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \approx 0.3$)], and in reflection mode [say, at $kL = 3.3$ ($\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \approx -0.3$)]. For example, the θ range of $r_{-1} > 0.65$ is above 65° for $kL = 3.3$. The capability of the DEG1 grating in demultiplexing is limited because the kL range of large r_{-1} is relatively narrow in this case. One of the key features here is that the areas of blazing for t_{-1} and r_{-1} do not overlap in the (kL, θ) -plane; i.e., transmission-mode blazing and reflection-mode blazing are separated in the parameter plane. To compare, Figs. 3(e) and 3(f) present r_{-1} and t_{-1} for the dielectric grating alone (called DG1). As observed, there are no features that might be inherited by the DEG1 grating. Notably, the effect of the order $m = 0$ for DG1 remains strong in the whole area in which the -1 st order may propagate. Also, for both EG1 and DEG1 gratings, the area of high r_{-1} involves a wide kL range in which the retroreflection regime ($\phi_{-1} = -\theta$) was obtained.

Next, we considered an alternate design, which differed from Fig. 3 in that the minimal thickness of the ENZ (part of the) grating was enlarged and the total thickness was decreased. As a result, these gratings have enhanced functional capability in the reflection mode but weakened capability of operation in the transmission mode. Figure 4 presents the results for t_{-1} and r_{-1} in the (kL, θ) -plane, for the three gratings: ENZ grating (EG2), hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating (DEG2), and dielectric grating (DG2). In Fig. 4(b), we observed a large area of $r_{-1} > 0.6$ for EG2, which occurred mainly for $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$. Compared to Fig. 3(b), the capability of high-efficiency demultiplexing and SF is enhanced, as far as r_{-1} reaches the maximum value of 0.85. In particular, the range of $4.1 < kL < 4.6$ is recommended for demultiplexing. For instance, $\theta = 45^\circ$ along with $kL = 4.0, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4,$ and 4.5 can be chosen. Correspondingly,

Fig. 4. (a) (c), and (e) Transmittance t_{-1} and (b), (d), and (f) reflectance r_{-1} on (kL, θ) plane for $D/L = 1.5$, $b/D = 0.68$, $h/D = 0.32$, $\omega_p L/c = 3.8$, and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$: (a) and (b) ENZ grating (EG2), (c) and (d) hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating (DEG2), and (e) and (f) dielectric grating (DG2). Insets show one structure's period: ENZ (black), dielectric (gray), and air (white).

$\theta_{-1} = -59.7^\circ, -55.6^\circ, -52.1^\circ, -48.9^\circ, -46.1^\circ,$ and -43.6° at these kL values. Notably, the same kL range is suitable for bandpass SF.

For the DEG2 grating, we observed a large area of $r_{-1} > 0.7$ in Fig. 4(d) that is suitable for multifunctional operation. It corresponds rather to $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} < 0$. This range is shifted toward a larger θ , similar to the case of EG1 and DEG1. It is widening compared to the EG2 grating at the price of abandoning the transmission mode for both EG2 and DEG2. For instance, SF with θ passbands of different widths for different but close kL values can be obtained here; e.g., $r_{-1} > 0.75$ when $\Delta\theta \approx 26^\circ$ and 32° , respectively, at $kL = 3.6$ and 3.7 . In these two cases, the range of variation of ϕ_{-1} is nearly the same as that of θ .

For the demultiplexing capability, it is important that $r_{-1} > 0.75$ in Fig. 4(d), within a wide kL range; i.e., $\Delta kL \approx 0.3, 0.36, 0.37,$ and 0.3 , at $\theta = 55^\circ, 60^\circ, 65^\circ,$ and 73° , respectively. For example, the values of $kL = 3.5, 3.6, 3.7,$ and 3.8 can be chosen at $\theta = 60^\circ$ for the four spectral components of the incident polychromatic wave to be demultiplexed. Then, the outgoing monochromatic waves will propagate at $\phi_{-1} = -68^\circ, -61.5^\circ, -56^\circ,$ and -52° , respectively. A similar situation will occur when several monochromatic waves corresponding to different kL values are incident either simultaneously or at different time instances.

To compare, Figs. 4(e) and 4(f) present the results for the DG2 dielectric grating, which represents the upper part of the DEG2 grating. Although r_{-1} remains small within the whole (kL, θ) area considered, it is obviously stronger at smaller kL

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Fig. 5. (a) (c), and (e) Transmittance t_{-1} and reflectance r_{-1} on (kL, θ) plane at $D/L = 1.0$, $b/D = 0.68$, and $b/D = 0.32$, $\omega_p L/c = 3.8$, and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$: (a) and (b) ENZ grating EG3, (c) and (d) hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating DEG3, and (e) and (f) dielectric grating DG3. Insets show one structure's period: ENZ (black), dielectric (gray), and air (white).

and larger θ . Therefore, the effects of stacking DG2 with EG2 that could appear for the DEG2 grating in Fig. 4(d) may be understood as a dramatic enhancement of the effects observed within the area of stronger r_{-1} in Fig. 4(f) that occurs due to the reflective nature of the ENZ dispersive material, and a further extension of this area due to the weak phase variations and relatively weak damping in the ENZ material.

Next, the results are presented in Fig. 5 for three gratings (EG3, DEG3, and DG3), which only differ from EG2, DEG2, and DG2 in that they have smaller thicknesses. Similar to the EG2 grating, the area of large r_{-1} occurs for the EG3 grating when $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$; however, similar to EG1, moderate values of r_{-1} are only achieved, which may restrict functional capability of this design. Generally speaking, the EG3 grating shows a lower overall blazing capability in the reflection mode than the EG1 and EG2 gratings.

For the DEG3 grating, $\max r_{-1} \approx 0.85$ is achieved while the area of $r_{-1} > 0.7$ in the (kL, θ) -plane comprises the ranges of $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} < 0$ and $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$. Crossing zero by $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ at increasing kL does not yield new features. This grating offers various regimes of bandpass SF with the width of the θ domain pass band that varies from 10° to 45° , depending on the choice of kL . Moreover, it obviously offers a better demultiplexing capability than DEG1 and DEG2 because the area of $r_{-1} > 0.75$ is larger for DEG3, which leads to a wider kL range. This makes possible demultiplexing simultaneously for several selected values of θ ; e.g., 50° , 60° , and 70° when $kL = 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 3.9, 4.0$, and 4.1 are chosen. For instance, for $\theta = 60^\circ$,

ϕ_{-1} is equal, respectively, to $-61.6^\circ, -56.3^\circ, -51.9^\circ, -48.2^\circ, -44.8^\circ$, and -41.8° . Along with a big freedom regarding demultiplexing, the DEG3 grating enables an unprecedentedly wide θ range in which the retroreflection regime is achieved. For example, we obtained $\phi_{-1} = -\theta = -55.8^\circ, -51.8^\circ$, and -48.4° , for $kL = 3.8, 4.0$, and 4.2 , respectively.

The diffraction properties of the DG3 grating observed in Fig. 5(f) are similar to those of DG2, so that the difference between DG3 and DEG3 can be said to be somehow inherited.

C. Case of More Than One Propagating Higher Order

Now let us consider the case in which not only the order $m = -1$ but also at least one or more higher orders are propagating. Generally, the more orders may propagate, the richer the variety of physical scenarios, but it is more difficult to forward the incident wave energy into a single outgoing wave. Diffraction efficiencies of individual orders are expected to be lower, so that is the reason to use more than one higher propagating order is rather obtaining positive values of ϕ_{-1} .

Figure 6 presents t_{-1} and r_{-1} in the (kL, θ) -plane for $\omega_p L/c = 2\pi$; i.e., in which the spectral location of the regime $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} = 0$ nearly coincides with the f domain threshold for $m = -1$ at $\theta = 0$. The geometrical parameters used here are chosen to be the same as the DEG3 grating in Figs. 5(c) and 5(d). We refer to this grating as DEG4. Interestingly, a narrowband increase of r_{-1} is observed in Fig. 6 at the kL values, which are just a bit smaller than the thresholds for the orders $m = -2$ and $m = +1$ (compare to Fig. 2), so that these features can formally be considered as some kind of Rayleigh–Wood anomalies [75].

The obtained results significantly differ from those in Figs. 3–5. The main feature observed in Fig. 6(b) is that the areas of high r_{-1} are narrow in both the θ domain and kL domain. Therefore, this design is suitable for dual narrow band-pass SF. Notably, r_0 can dominate r_{-1} within a wide area of the (kL, θ) -plane, in which the order $m = -1$ may propagate. In turn, the transmission is relatively weak and shows a rather narrowband or both narrowband and wideband features for $m = 0$ (not shown) and $m = -1$ [Fig. 6(a)], respectively. It is observed that, similar to r_{-1} , the anomalies manifest themselves for t_{-1} at the -2 nd order threshold; however, in contrast to r_{-1} , there is no signature of the anomalies for t_{-1} at the $+1$ st order threshold.

Finally, Fig. 7 presents r_{-1} and t_{-1} in the (kL, θ) -plane for $\omega_p L/c = 7.8$ for the geometric parameters chosen as in Fig. 3, except for the D/L -value that is taken now as 1. The ENZ,

Fig. 6. (a) Transmittance t_{-1} and (b) reflectance r_{-1} on (kL, θ) -plane for hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating (DEG4) for $D/L = 1.0$, $b/D = 0.68$, $b/D = 0.32$, $\omega_p L/c = 2\pi$, and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$. Insets show one structure's period: ENZ (black) and dielectric (gray).

Fig. 7. (a), (c), and (e) Transmittance t_{-1} and (b), (d), and (f) reflectance r_{-1} on (kL, θ) -plane for $D/L = 1.0$, $b/D = 0.50$, $h/D = 0.40$, $\omega_p L/c = 7.8$, and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$ for: (a)–(b) ENZ grating (EG5), (c)–(d) hybrid dielectric-ENZ grating (DEG5), and (e) and (f) dielectric grating (DG5). White circles indicate the wide kL -range maxima of r_{-1} , which can be attributed to Rayleigh–Wood anomalies. Insets show one structure’s period: ENZ (black), dielectric (gray), and air (white).

dielectric-ENZ, and dielectric gratings were studied here, which are denoted by EG5, DEG5, and DG5, respectively. In Fig. 7(a), a wide area of $t_{-1} > 0.3$ was observed for EG5 in the (kL, θ) -plane at a smaller θ than in Figs. 3(a) and 5(a); i.e., in the vicinity of $\theta = 25^\circ$. A comparison to Fig. 2 indicates that in this area the -1 st order is the only propagating order. On the contrary, the area of $r_{-1} > 0.15$ appears in Fig. 7(b) above the -2 nd order threshold. In particular, we obtained more unusual shapes in the area of significant t_{-1} and r_{-1} , both of which are located below the -2 nd order threshold. The areas mentioned above occur at $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}} \geq 0$. For the DG5 grating, we obtained large areas of $t_{-1} > 0.4$, whereas $r_{-1} > 0.25$ is achieved only within narrow ranges of kL and θ variations. To compare, Figs. 7(e) and 7(f) present t_{-1} and r_{-1} for the DG5 grating. The diffraction anomalies constitute the main features for r_{-1} . A part of them are located close to the thresholds but at a bit smaller values of kL for given θ (compare to Fig. 2), so that they can also be attributed to the Rayleigh–Wood anomalies [75]. However, no direct inheriting of the features observed in Figs. 7(e) and 7(f) can be recognized in Figs. 7(c) and 7(d).

Comparing Figs. 3–7, we come to three conclusions: (i) Switching between various operation regimes can be obtained by means of θ variation; (ii) The achievable functionalities include demultiplexing, spatial filtering and retroreflection; and (iii) The ranges with negative and positive near-zero values of

$\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ can almost equally contribute to the obtained wide-band and wide-angle blazing. Note that the order $m = 0$ can also be used for low-pass/bandstop SF in the same gratings. This may reinforce the overall capability of multifunctional operation.

D. Asymmetry in Reflection and Effects of Losses

If the structures show a breaking of spatial inversion symmetry, AT and asymmetric reflection are possible, which means that the wave processes may be significantly different at the forward and backward incidence. As follows from the obtained results, in the studied gratings AT is weak but asymmetric reflection is well pronounced. For the forward illumination, we assumed that $\theta_{\text{fw}} = \theta$, where θ is the incidence angle as defined in Fig. 1. For the backward illumination, we take $\theta_{\text{bw}} = \theta_{\text{fw}} + \pi$. In addition, the effect of losses in the ENZ material on r_m was considered here. In line with the Lorentz reciprocity, $T^{\rightarrow} + R^{\rightarrow} + A^{\rightarrow} = T^{\leftarrow} + R^{\leftarrow} + A^{\leftarrow}$, where arrows \leftarrow and \rightarrow stand for the forward and the backward illumination cases, respectively. When only the zero order may propagate, $r_0^{\rightarrow} + A^{\rightarrow} = r_0^{\leftarrow} + A^{\leftarrow}$, because $t_0 = t_0^{\rightarrow} = t_0^{\leftarrow}$ [19]. In the general case, it is possible that $r_0^{\rightarrow} \neq r_0^{\leftarrow}$.

Figure 8 presents r_0 and r_{-1} versus kL for the EG2 and DEG2 gratings. It is observed that strong diffractions may appear only if the grating is illuminated from the side of the flat air–ENZ interface. It occurs for both gratings, for all three values of γ/ω_p , so that asymmetric reflection is a common feature. Moreover, there are spectral regimes in which the incident-wave energy is mainly taken by the order $m = -1$ in the forward-illumination case and by the order $m = 0$ in the backward-illumination case. In Fig. 8(a), it is observed for the EG2 grating that small positive values of ε_{ENZ} are sufficient for strong blazing, so that high- ε dielectrics, surface plasmons, or guided-mode resonances, like those in [46,53], are not needed.

As shown in Figs. 8(b) and 8(c) for the DEG2 grating, stacking of the ENZ and dielectric gratings and adjustment of θ allow positioning of $\max r_{-1}$ at a rather arbitrary kL value, so that the blazing region can be shifted from negative to zero, and then to positive $\text{Re } \varepsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ just by varying θ . As observed, the increase of γ/ω_p from 0.01 to 0.2 leads to a nearly twofold decrease of r_{-1}^{\rightarrow} , but all basic features remain the same even when $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.2$. Spectral locations of $\max r_{-1}^{\rightarrow}$ are kept while varying γ/ω_p and the capability of asymmetry in reflection is conserved.

A rather strong asymmetry in absorption occurred in all three cases in Fig. 8 (not shown). For instance, in Fig. 8(b), $A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow} > 5$ at $kL = 3.95$ and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.2$, while $A^{\leftarrow} < 0.1$ for the entire kL – range considered here. Generally, the contrast $A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow}$ is higher for the DEG2 grating than for the EG2 grating. A sharp peak of A^{\rightarrow} that appears at the Rayleigh–Wood anomaly is noticeable. In the case of the parameter set used in Fig. 8(c) does it yield the largest values for A^{\rightarrow} and $A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow}$.

Figure 9 presents r_0 and r_{-1} versus kL for the DEG3 grating. Spectrally wider ranges of blazing and asymmetric reflection are achieved here despite of a relatively large θ -value, compare to Fig. 8(b). Furthermore, the regime of $r_0 \approx 0$ is common for all three values of γ/ω_p , in contrast with Fig. 8(b). Here, this regime is obtained at $kL \approx 4$. In turn, $\max A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow}$ is observed near $kL = 4.25$ (not shown).

Fig. 8. Reflectance r_0 and r_{-1} versus kL for the gratings: (a) EG2 and (b) and (c) DEG2, at (a) and (c) $\theta = 50^\circ$ and (b) $\theta = 70^\circ$. Solid blue lines r_0^\rightarrow , dashed red/violet lines r_{-1}^\rightarrow , dash-dotted green lines r_0^\leftarrow , and dashed gray lines $r_{-1}^\leftarrow \approx 0$ (they superimpose with the abscissa axis). For r_0^\rightarrow , r_{-1}^\rightarrow , r_0^\leftarrow , and r_{-1}^\leftarrow , most thick, mid-thick, and thin lines correspond to $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01, 0.05$, and 0.2 , respectively.

Fig. 9. Reflectance r_0 and r_{-1} for the DEG3 grating at $\theta = 70^\circ$. Solid blue lines r_0^\rightarrow , dashed red/violet lines r_{-1}^\rightarrow , dash-dotted green lines r_0^\leftarrow , and dashed gray lines $r_{-1}^\leftarrow \approx 0$ (they superimpose with the abscissa axis). For r_0^\rightarrow , r_{-1}^\rightarrow , r_0^\leftarrow , r_{-1}^\leftarrow , most thick, mid-thick, and thin lines correspond to $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01, 0.05$, and 0.2 , respectively.

Fig. 10. Reflectance r_0 and r_{-1} versus θ for the DEG3 grating at: (a) $kL = 3.8$ and (b) $kL = 4.15$. Solid blue lines r_0^\rightarrow , dashed red/violet lines r_{-1}^\rightarrow , dash-dotted green lines r_0^\leftarrow , and dashed gray lines $r_{-1}^\leftarrow \approx 0$ (they superimpose with the abscissa axis). For r_0^\rightarrow , r_{-1}^\rightarrow , r_0^\leftarrow , and r_{-1}^\leftarrow , most thick, mid-thick, and thin lines correspond to $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01, 0.05$, and 0.2 , respectively.

Figure 10 presents r_0 and r_{-1} versus θ for given kL . As observed, the -1 st order and 0th order dominate, correspondingly, in the forward and in the backward illumination cases when $\theta > \theta_{th}$ (θ_{th} is the angle starting from which the -1 st order becomes propagating) that leads to a strongly pronounced asymmetry in reflection. While r_0 is suppressed within a wide range of θ variation, r_{-1} is nearly constant for both $kL = 3.8$ at which $\omega = \omega_p$ (i.e., $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} = 0$) and $kL = 4.15$ at which $\omega > \omega_p$ ($\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}} > 0$). A sharp switching between r_0 and r_{-1} that occurs at $\theta = \theta_{th}$ is observed, similarly to the hypothetical dispersion-free case [72].

Note that transmission is moderately high at small θ but becomes weaker at large θ . As a result, asymmetric reflection may show a higher contrast at larger θ , including the angles

being close to the grazing ones. Moreover, the difference between $r_0^\rightarrow + r_{-1}^\rightarrow$ and $r_0^\leftarrow + r_{-1}^\leftarrow$ can be stronger at the large θ , so a nearly twofold difference can be achieved, as observed in Fig. 10(b). Interestingly, there are accident (kL, θ) -pairs, for which $r_{-1}^\rightarrow = r_0^\leftarrow$ whereas $r_0^\rightarrow \approx 0$ and $r_{-1}^\leftarrow \approx 0$, as occurs in the vicinity of $\theta = 40^\circ$ for $kL = 4.15$.

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Fig. 11. Transmittance t_0 and t_{-1} versus kL for the DEG1 grating at $\theta = 45^\circ$. For $t_0^{\rightarrow}, t_{-1}^{\rightarrow}, t_0^{\leftarrow}$, and t_{-1}^{\leftarrow} , most thick, mid-thick, and thin lines correspond to $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01, 0.05$, and 0.2 .

In addition, for the DEG3 grating asymmetry in absorption is well pronounced for the parameter sets used in both Figs. 10(a) and 10(b). In particular, $A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow} > 4$ at $\theta = 80^\circ$ when $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.2$. At the same time, the contrast $A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow}$ at the Rayleigh–Wood anomalies is not the highest one, as far as the peaks of both A^{\rightarrow} and A^{\leftarrow} do appear. For both Figs. 10(a) and 10(b), the contrast is largest at $\theta = 80^\circ$ and expected to be even larger at larger θ .

Figure 11 presents t_0 and t_{-1} versus kL for the DEG1 grating, and shows that asymmetry in transmission is not well pronounced, in spite of the fact that the structure's symmetry is broken. To compare, for the DEG2 and DEG3 gratings, the ratio $t_{-1}^{\rightarrow}/t_{-1}^{\leftarrow}$ can be larger, but the transmission efficiency is rather weak, so that these regimes are inappropriate for use in AT devices. However, this is not a common rule, so that AT can be achieved for another similar design. In addition, the surface plasmon resonance arising at $kL \approx 3.5$ is noticeable in that it yields $t_0 \approx 0$ at $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.01$ and $\gamma/\omega_p = 0.05$. The increase of γ/ω_p from 0.01 to 0.2 results in a nearly twofold decrease of $\max t_{-1}$ at $kL = 4.6$. For the parameter set in Fig. 11, $\max\{A^{\leftarrow}/A^{\rightarrow}, A^{\rightarrow}/A^{\leftarrow}\}$ is less than 2, despite the peak of A^{\rightarrow} that appears at the Rayleigh–Wood anomaly. Notably, for the parameter sets used in Figs. 10 and 11, there are accident regimes with $A^{\rightarrow} = A^{\leftarrow}$. For instance, it occurs in the vicinity of $\theta = 35^\circ$ for the parameter set in Fig. 10(b).

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS

To summarize, we studied the diffraction properties of the metagratings enabled by ENZ materials. The key result is that the wideband and simultaneously wide-angle -1 st order blazing (deflection) is a common feature that does not need a sophisticated adjustment of the geometric parameters. However, there is a strong effect of the grating's height-to-period ratio and of the presence or absence of a dielectric component on the appearance of the area of strong blazing on the (kL, θ) -plane. This component may be needed to achieve a particular size and location of the aforementioned area. According to the obtained results, the width of the θ range in which strong blazing can be achieved is up to 40° and that enables efficient bandpass SF. In turn, the width of the kL range is up to 0.6 within the area that

is considered as a proper condition to obtain spatial demultiplexing. Retroreflection can be obtained for a wide kL and θ dependent range of the outgoing-wave angle within the blazing area. Stacking the ENZ and dielectric gratings also enables blazing at large incidence angles and yields the efficient transfer of the incident-wave energy to one of the higher diffraction orders, which takes place while there is no corrugations at the outer boundaries. The high capability of the studied metagratings in reflection is predetermined by the high reflectivity of the ENZ material. Designing the structures with intermittent regions of larger and smaller thicknesses allows us to suitably distribute the incident-wave energy between transmission and the reflection.

The range of either negative or positive $\text{Re } \epsilon_{\text{ENZ}}$ or both can contribute to the resulting blazing. From the blazing perspective, it is crucial which side of the grating is illuminated. If it is illuminated from the side of the flat air–ENZ interface, no blazing will take place. The inner corrugations like the ones used in the studied dielectric–ENZ gratings by no means worsen the capability in wideband/wide-angle blazing, but the structure should be illuminated from the side of the air–dielectric (noncorrugated outer) interface. These features predetermine the high capability in asymmetric reflection, whereas efficient asymmetric transmission has not been found in the studied structures. The results indicate that the dielectric–ENZ gratings (denoted as DEGs) show a richer variety of diffraction effects than the ENZ gratings (denoted as EGs). The obtained deflection features are quite robust with respect to the variations of losses of the ENZ material. Therefore, some natural materials like tunable phase-change materials and polar dielectrics should be assessed for possible use as the ENZ components in our metagratings.

The choice of material for the ENZ component and fabrication techniques depends on the aimed functionality and frequency range. Realization of the ENZ component via a wire medium for the both EGs and DEGs may need standard fabrication techniques applicable to wire arrays, that depend on the chosen frequency range, which may be taken at least from microwaves to visible. The situation is similar when either a homogeneous material, like a phase-change material or a polar dielectric, is used for the ENZ component, say, at the far-/mid-IR, or a metal–dielectric multilayer composite is used at the near-IR or visible. A part of the techniques are reviewed in [26]. Notably, lamellar corrugations might be more consistent with the available fabrication techniques, so it is worth providing a change of the sinusoidal shape for the lamellar one. Fabrication of the DEGs comprising two layers made of nonstructured natural materials can be simplified if, in addition to lamellar corrugations, the ENZ layer is noncorrugated, and the diffraction-enabling interface is the outer dielectric–air interface, instead of the inner dielectric–ENZ interface. Therefore, an additional study is planned to clarify the possible differences between the DEGs in this paper and similar dielectric–ENZ gratings with corrugations placed only at the dielectric–air interface. However, since the key functionality-enabling features (i.e., presence of an ENZ layer, corrugations of the dielectric layer, and broken spatial inversion symmetry) are the same in such modified lamellar structures as in the studied metagratings with sinusoidal corrugations, conservation of the basic diffraction features and functional capability can be expected.

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